

FDO – Upload of FDO

Version 1.1

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<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1NkkdiIsIxCrvexSKtQXIPopMhE7nHOpd8X4m-3YJ5s/edit?usp=sharing>

Previous Version: [PEN-FDO-Upload-1.0-20220608](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1fDR5VHbVla2AbLsBR58idrfn_Ib3x6Fk-LJ4c_Ftt4/edit#)

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1fDR5VHbVla2AbLsBR58idrfn_Ib3x6Fk-LJ4c_Ftt4/edit#

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Abstract

This document illustrates the type of operations and checks that need to be done when an FDO or a set of FDOs of two specific FDO configuration types¹ are being uploaded to the domain of FDOs. It also indicates the type of services that can be thought of at different FDO levels (PID, PID record information, metadata and content based). Finally, it describes the scope of checks that can be carried out at different levels (PID, metadata, bit-sequence). A special problem is indicated that is related to the fact that the community-based metadata can include references that are relevant for FDO level checks. A suggestion is made on how to bridge between semantic spaces.

¹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1r61y4am9Bx01P38LMbR68KL-hYhGYiPw/edit#heading=h.gidqxs>

Status of this document

This document has been turned into a PEN1.1 document from an earlier version without modifications - no further comments were made.

Acknowledgments

This document is based on the discussions within TSIG, therefore we thank all TSIG members for their contributions.

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1. Recommendations

This document is not normative in the sense of adding specifications to the Full FDO Specification. It is more of an illustration about the kinds of procedures that are involved when a new FDO or a set of new FDOs will be uploaded to the known domain of FDOs. The FDO Forum needs to offer a set of recipes for different cases, the Upload Cases point in the direction of such recipes.

In addition this document indicates the layers at which services can be thought of and how metadata elements provided by the community and crucial for FDO level processing could be integrated into the FDO world.

2. Introduction

When discussing what an FDO is we often compare the mechanisms with those invented for the Internet. One of the metaphors is “plug-in”, i.e. before a new device type can be plugged into the Internet, running TCP/IP tests will be carried out to check TCP/IP compliance as long as the protocol requirements are met. The result is that all device users can immediately plug-in that device to the Internet and connect instantly to everyone in the world. This concept should be valid for FDOs of course, but we then need to say what “FDO-uploading” exactly implies.

We need to make a few assumptions:

- We have trustworthy repositories ready to hold and manage FDOs assuming in this paper a DO based approach for reasons of simplicity. In accordance with documents such as Turning FAIR into Reality [1] see as instances to manage and register FDOs in contrast to local stores on notebook, servers etc.
- The base definition of FDOs is supported [2], i.e., FDOs are assigned a PID and associated with metadata (MD) of different kinds.
- Metadata ideally will include simple key MD², descriptive MD, deep scientific MD, provenance MD, license MD, access permission MD etc.³
- The PID is the entity that binds all information needed to make an FDO FAIR together which includes the above-mentioned MD components, i.e., it has attributes that include references.
- MD schemas and usages are widely defined by the user community and will vary in their richness⁴.

² We call now key metadata those metadata elements which are required at FDO level. Normally, it will be a part of the descriptive metadata. Often communities do not make a difference between descriptive and deep scientific metadata.

³ There may be even more metadata such as transaction records etc. Provenance MD is being subsumed under deep scientific metadata.

⁴ The degree of richness is not relevant at FDO level as long as specific information necessary for FDO validation is provided.

- The Identifier Resolution Protocol (IRP) [3] and Digital Object Interface Protocol (DOIP) [4] are being used to interface with the PID system resp. with the repository.

3. Upload and Ingest

3.1 User Upload Case A

In this case we assume that the metadata is not covered as a separate FDO but contained in some databases.

A user has a bit-sequence encoding certain content according to some schema stored in a file and created appropriate metadata according to some schema and wants to upload it into the repository as a valid FDO. The upload & ingest function will carry out the following tasks:

1. Upload descriptive and scientific metadata and check schema compliance
2. Upload license and access permission statements and check schema compliance
3. Upload the bit-sequence, check type consistency (specifications in MD, file ending, check content format) and extract “type”
4. Create a new FDO and ingest it to the holding
 - a. Extract some key metadata, store bit-sequence in store, extract path information, add license information to metadata, store metadata in database, store access permission metadata in ACLs
 - b. Create the PID Kernel Information according to a PID profile⁵, request the Handle by providing the kernel information
 - c) Update the key metadata with the PID
5. Offer the PID to a Resoucesync⁶ type of service every repository needs to support. It could be an internal resource which itself is an FDO which can be questioned by DOIP operations such as “give me the list of all FDO” or “give me the most recent list of new FDOs” etc.

3.2 User Upload Case B

Basically, it is the same kind of operation, but some repositories might prefer to ingest also the metadata as an FDO which would increase FDO compliance (F1). The steps to be taken are

⁵ We refer to the FDO [WD-PIDProfileAttributes-1.0-20220317](https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1A0DXmwNnloRzhMeeJeUvcmoGBFPGdnWU) WD:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1A0DXmwNnloRzhMeeJeUvcmoGBFPGdnWU>

⁶ ResourceSync (<http://www.openarchives.org/rs/toc>) is just mentioned as one option to indicate availability.

almost the same, however, with a major difference: now we have two FDOs which need to relate to each other (see the diagram).

Having both relations is important since two basic access paths need to be supported: (1) One gets the PID of an FDO and then also needs access to metadata. (2) A search is being carried out and one finds a set of metadata records. From these MD records representing the content of the MD FDO it must be possible to access the FDO.

In the following we will not use this way of setting up the repository, but the one discussed in case A.

3.3 Advanced Upload Scenarios

Here, we sketch three advanced scenarios of the FDO-Upload concept which need to be worked out in more detail. These scenarios are inspired by papers from Beretta et.al. and Doctorow⁷.

Scientist “A” publishes a “chlorophyll concentration” dataset “X” from a specific region as FAIR Digital Object. The dataset includes machine readable descriptions of chlorophyll and chlorophyll concentration. Scientist “B” wants to use dataset “X” to understand the impact of chlorophyll concentration on a particular fish species. Without knowing or caring to know about the data standards and specifications of dataset X, Scientist B can upload elements of chlorophyll concentration data with fish species observational data.

⁷ Beretta, V., Desconnets, J.C., Mougnot, I., Arslan, M., Barde, J. and Chaffard, V., 2021. A user-centric metadata model to foster sharing and reuse of multidisciplinary datasets in environmental and life sciences. *Computers & Geosciences*, 154, p.104807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2021.104807>. Also see Doctorow, C., 2021. Competitive compatibility: let's fix the internet, not the tech giants. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(10), pp.26-29. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3446789>

Scientist “A” publishes a “chlorophyll concentration” dataset “X” from a specific region as FAIR Digital Object. Along with the dataset, there are also descriptions of the API that can make use of the dataset. Scientist “A” works with Scientist “B” from another domain who is interested to know the impact of chlorophyll concentration on a particular fish species. B also publishes data as FAIR Digital Object and has an API. A & B worked together to upload the Digital Objects via API and publish a new set of FAIR Digital Object dataset “Y”.

A commercial entity “C” provides paid services for earth observation satellite data. The dataset is proprietary and not conforming to any standards. Initially, “C” is not interested in making datasets interoperable as their business case depends on the closed format. “A” and “B” both need these datasets for research purposes. They show a use case and demand for interoperability and upload based on the newly created dataset FAIR Digital Object “Y”. This FAIR Digital Object upload model shows that “C” can expand the use of their services (the services can still be paid but conforming to a standard) and agrees to allow uploads.

To make such advanced upload examples into reality, smart operations need to be provided and linked with the corresponding data types. Users would simply select operations to be carried out and all underlying mechanisms are transparent to them. It is the encapsulation capability inherent to FDOs that allows users to link operations with types that can be selected depending on the contexts and the users’ intentions.

4. Services and Checks

It is obvious that the above procedure creates almost 100% FDOs. We can run services at different levels using the available information and we can check FDO compliance.

4.1 Services

Any type of service that has the required access permissions and complies with the license statements can now make use of the data stored. To give a few examples:

- some services could be built on top of accessing the PID and the Kernel information included such as tracing (if hash codes are being used for example), indicating duplications, etc.
- some services could just resolve the PIDs and use the metadata to support searching⁸, doing statistical calculations on MD, build virtual collections, etc.
- some services could indeed extract and check the type, relate it to operations and execute them

⁸ We assume many search portals maintained by brokers specialising on certain data profiles. They will run crawlers checking the offering from a specific set of repositories.

So we have a cascade of service types all possible through the FDO approach that keeps all information together:

- services just using the PID
- services using the PID and the metadata
- services using the PID, metadata and the bit-sequence

4.2 Upload Checks

Checks can occur at two levels:

- first the repository needs to support suitable mechanisms as described
- then each FDO needs to fulfill certain requirements (which should be widely given if the repositories ingest procedures are correct)

Here we will only talk about the FDO level checks and do not care about all kinds of metadata categories which are used to describe properties of the FDO which are relevant for scientific interpretation such as creators, dates, language spoken, energy levels being measured etc etc. Communities are partly using many different categories and we cannot influence the schemas and practices in communities. In general, categories being used in community metadata are not made to be machine actionable yet.

The FDO level checks include the following aspects:

- Does the PID resolution lead to a set of kernel information values?
- Can all these values be interpreted since they have been defined and registered, and are part of a specified PID profile?
- Can the (key, descriptive, scientific, license) metadata be accessed using the path description in the PID record?
- Can the metadata be parsed using the schema definition?
- Can the license specification be identified in the metadata and be interpreted given an ontology (such as CC) and is the license coherent?
- Can the access permissions be found and are they readable?
- Can the bit-sequence of the FDO be accessed if the PID record includes a reference to it and given appropriate access permissions?
- Is the type found in the bit-sequence coherent with the Type as specified in the PID record?

How can we bridge between categories needed at FDO level and the actual categories as they are being used in community metadata schemas? One suggestion is to maintain a shared FDO Level Ontology which includes all categories that are needed and an FDO Mapping Registry⁹ that maps them to community categories. The following diagram indicates the needed infrastructure. The FDO ontology would not only include typical categories as they may occur in

⁹ Here the mapping registry as suggested by SEMAF can be used.

the PID record (Kernel Information) but also as they may occur in the metadata, but nevertheless needed for FDO level checks. Typically, the Data Type Registry would be used to define and register these categories independent of where they may occur.

- Bit_Seq_Ref Reference to the bit-sequence
- MD_Ref Metadata Reference
- License_Ref Reference to license information
- Acc_Rights_Ref Reference to find the access rights
- etc.

The mapping registry would simply tell the testing software that if it looks for access rights information according to the FDO Ontology one would find it under a specific category as it is used in the schema provided by community X. Creating such a mapping registry is feasible, since the number of categories relevant at FDO level is limited.

5. Changes from previous versions

This version 1.0 has the status of a WD to be discussed in the FDO Forum. The following changes were made from the TSIG Internal version:

- The FDO Document Template was used.
- A Conclusion chapter was added with the intention to indicate the essentials that may be included in the FDO Specification document.

- An error in chapter numbering was corrected: “3” became “2.6”

The change history of the TSIG internal document is indicated in this table:

Version			
TSIG Internal 1.0	TSIG Editing team	20.3.2022	- transformed and edited from an internal TSIG discussion document - some references were added - a few typos were corrected
PEN 1.0	Editors	7.6.2022	- no further comments were made
PEN1.1	Editors	17.10.2022	- no further comments were made

References

[1] Turning FAIR into Reality:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf

[2] FDO base definition:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ivvg3C_QWSO9PIQwkKT89xG4fBhNAs7_6b0Dz11EwDg/edit

[3] Identifier Resolution Protocol (IRP): internal communication

[4] Digital Object Interface Protocol (DOIP):

https://www.dona.net/sites/default/files/2018-11/DOIPv2Spec_1.pdf